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Independent Crusaders Mapping Project

The *Independent Crusaders Mapping Project* takes advantage of emerging digital tools to shed light on individuals who assumed the identity of crusader and traveled to the Latin Kingdom of Jerusalem outside of the major, canonical crusades. Biographical [profile pages \(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/profile-pages\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/profile-pages) contextualize the expeditions of these independent crusaders and their companions, and interactive transcriptions of [Latin charters \(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/charters\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/charters) demonstrate the ways in which they declared their desire to travel to the Holy Land. The [dynamic map \(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/icp-map\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/icp-map) visualizes the project's data by charting the departures of the crusaders over time. [Intrepretive essays \(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/interpreting-the-project\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/interpreting-the-project) offer avenues to understand the project and utilize it in the classroom, and all of the website's [data \(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/download-our-data\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/download-our-data) is freely accessible for users to view and repurpose for their own research.

[Explore the departure map](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/icp-map)

[\(https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/icp-map\)](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/icp-map)

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[Learn about the crusaders](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/profile-pages)

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[View the interactive charters](https://medievalomeka.ace.fordham.edu/exhibits/show/independent-crusaders-project/charters)

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Because the majority of these crusaders lived in Francophone continental Europe, users are encouraged to explore the [French of Outremer Project](http://legacy.fordham.edu/academics/programs%20at%20fordham/medieval%20studies/french%20of%20outremer/index.asp), another digital resource from Fordham's [Center for Medieval Studies \(https://medievaldigital.ace.fordham.edu/\)](https://medievaldigital.ace.fordham.edu/), for a look into how medieval Western communities imagined *la terre d'outremer* in their literary texts.

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